

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Paper on "Digitainability Concept Evolution in Fashion Industry: A Bibliometric Analysis"

SPOKE N 3 – Tourism and culture industry

Flagship project CIRIL - DELIVERABLE D. 2.1

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.

Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. Introduction

1.1 The digital innovation and sustainability: a background

The ongoing societal and economic changes aligned with industrial paradigms are continually examined by scientists, researchers, scholars, and practitioners. Their collective aim is to identify opportunities for achieving sustainable future goals. According to a 2021 report by the European Commission, there is a recognized transition in the industrial paradigm from Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0. This transition entails modifications in guiding principles and operational strategies. Since 2011, Industry 4.0 has highlighted the importance of digital technologies in enabling agile manufacturing and improving industrial and business process efficiency. In contrast, Industry 5.0 builds upon 4.0 by emphasizing research and innovation to create sustainable, resilient, and human-centric industries. It is based on socially and environmentally oriented technologies, advanced digitalization, and AI applications (Breque et al., 2021). This shift has led to the concept of "Digitainability," a forward-looking approach to industrial development that promotes transparency and intelligence within processes to enhance efficiency, achieve sustainability, and support industry resilience (Shashi, 2022). Theoretical frameworks suggest that sustainability drives these processes, while digitalization provides digital tools to gain a competitive edge through innovation in products, processes, and business models. One industry undergoing a notable shift from resource-intensive to energy-efficient and sustainability-oriented practices is the fashion industry. Digital transformation is seen as a crucial asset capable of reshaping the industry into a more sustainable entity (Colombi and D'Itria, 2023). The modern fashion landscape is characterized by significant changes in operational principles, leveraging digitalization to address ecological and societal issues such as reducing carbon emissions, curbing overconsumption, efficient stock management, and recycling. This transformation penetrates deep into industrial processes,

influencing product development and prompting a reevaluation of business models.

Digital manufacturing enables the creation of smart supply chain networks by leveraging digital technologies to establish an integrated system that connects various stakeholders in real-time. This approach involves rapid interaction, collaboration, knowledge sharing, and necessitates the development of new business models, including those driven by digital circularity. In the fashion industry, digital-based smart networks enhance communication, transforming interactions between companies and consumers to encourage responsible production and conscious consumption (Mokhtari et al., 2020). These networks also explore the interaction between physical and virtual spaces and the use of augmented reality. Moreover, social media in the fashion industry functions not only as a platform for e-commerce and digital marketing but also as incubators for cyber business, fostering process innovations (Lueg et al., 2015).

Given these dynamics, the fashion industry is an exciting context for discussing the potential to establish a digital ecosystem aligned with Industry 5.0 principles. This ecosystem would boost the industry's competitiveness by utilizing advanced digitalization, big data, and artificial intelligence. In the near future, the demand for advanced digitalization, combined with the need to incorporate circularity principles into textile and apparel manufacturing, presents sustainability challenges that the fashion industry must address through innovation at every stage of the value chain.

Considering these factors, this paper aims to provide comprehensive and structured insights into the evolution of studies on the conceptual aspects of digitally driven transformations in the fashion industry from an Industry 5.0 perspective. It seeks to highlight the sustainability potential of digital transformation within the industry, focusing on product, process, and business model innovation prompted by the sustainability-oriented benefits of digital transformation. Specifically, within the Digitainability framework, the paper conducts a bibliometric analysis of 277 academic papers from peer-reviewed scientific journals. The methodological approach used in analyzing the bibliometric results allows for identifying the most influential papers in the field to achieve the following tasks: uncover gaps in the scientific systematization and

exploration of digital tool applications in the industry; prepare a systematic foundation for further development of the advanced digitalization concept regarding three main areas—product, process, and business model innovation; and discover the potential of digitalization during the transition stage of industrial sustainability paradigms beyond Industry 4.0 for future academic research and practical implementation. The modern context of fashion industry development and further elaborated digitainability conceptual framework description are introduced on the figure 1 and figure 2 accordingly.

Fig. 1 - Modern concept of fashion industry development

Fig. 2 – Digitainability Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

2.1 Methodology and data

In this Bibliometric Review, we have strategically chosen to conduct an in-depth analysis of the ten most cited papers within our dataset. By focusing on these highly influential works, we aim to deeply understand their contributions to the research field. Our analysis will include a thorough examination of each paper's objectives, results, methodologies, and limitations. Understanding these papers' aims will provide crucial insights into the key research questions and challenges addressed by the authors. Analyzing the results will help us identify significant findings and contributions that have shaped the field's knowledge base. Furthermore, examining the methods used will allow us to assess the rigor and validity of the research approaches. Finally, recognizing the limitations of each paper will offer valuable context for interpreting the results and identifying areas for further investigation. Through this focused analysis, we aim to highlight the most impactful and groundbreaking works, shedding light on the evolution and advancement of knowledge within the research domain.

The present study employs a Bibliometric Review to comprehensively analyze scholarly literature in a specific research domain over a 24-year period, from 1998 to 2022. The dataset comprises 277 academic papers collected from Scopus, a reputable multidisciplinary abstract and citation

database. Our objective is to gain valuable insights into the evolution of the research domain and identify influential works, prolific authors, and emerging research trends. The first step involves data preprocessing to ensure data integrity and consistency, including removing duplicates, verifying metadata accuracy, and addressing missing information. By meticulously curating the dataset, we ensure the reliability and validity of the subsequent bibliometric analysis.

Using the R programming language, we employ the Bibliometrix package to compute various bibliometric indicators. Citation analysis assesses the impact and visibility of individual papers and authors within the research domain, revealing highly cited works and influential authors who have made substantial contributions to the field. Furthermore, co-authorship analysis identifies collaborative networks among researchers and institutions, highlighting patterns of collaboration and knowledge sharing, offering insights into the structure and dynamics of the research community. Examining keyword co-occurrence patterns provides an in-depth understanding of prevalent research themes and their interconnections, unveiling emerging trends and key topics that have gained significance over time. Additionally, temporal analysis examines publication trends, identifying periods of rapid growth or shifts in research focus. This temporal assessment helps us grasp the historical developments within the research domain and discern any turning points or transformative phases.

The findings of this Bibliometric Review will be presented through descriptive statistics, data visualizations, and interactive graphical representations, offering a clear and intuitive overview of the research domain's landscape and evolution, enabling researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders to grasp the most crucial insights.

The study spans 1998 to July 31, 2023, analyzing 277 academic papers sourced from Scopus using keywords like "fashion," "textile and apparel," "digitalization," "digital," "AI," "3D," "big data," "machine learning," "innovation," and "innovative." Initially, the database included 721 documents, but 444 were excluded after a preliminary analysis due to their irrelevance to the study. By meticulously curating the dataset, we ensure the reliability and validity of the bibliometric analysis that follows. The part of the descriptive statistics is presented on the figure 3.

Fig. 3 – Descriptive statistics.

In addition to bibliometric indicators, we enrich our analysis with a content review of the ten most cited papers (figure 4). This approach allows us to systematize the sustainability perspectives discussed directly or indirectly in these papers, which focus on innovation and digitalization in the fashion industry. This content analysis helps uncover the theoretical background of the Digitainability framework, providing a comprehensive understanding of the sustainability potential of digital transformation in this field.

- Matarazzo, M., Penco, L., Profumo, G., & Quaglia, R. (2021). Digital transformation and customer value creation in Made in Italy SMEs: A dynamic capabilities perspective. *Journal of Business Research*, 123, 642-656.
- Scuotto, V., Del Giudice, M., Della Peruta, M. R., & Tarba, S. (2017). The performance implications of leveraging internal innovation through social media networks: An empirical verification of the smart fashion industry. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 120, 184-194.
- Vehmas, K., Raudaskoski, A., Heikkilä, P., Harlin, A., & Mensonen, A. (2018). Consumer attitudes and communication in circular fashion. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 22(3), 286-300.
- Sandvik, I. M., & Stubbs, W. (2019). Circular fashion supply chain through textile-to-textile recycling. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 23(3), 366-381.
- Silva, E. S., & Bonetti, F. (2021). Digital humans in fashion: Will consumers interact?. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 60, 102430
- Bertola, P., & Teunissen, J. (2018). Fashion 4.0. Innovating fashion industry through digital transformation. *Research Journal of Textile and Apparel*, 22(4), 352-369.
- Shrivastava, A., Jain, G., Kamble, S. S., & Belhadi, A. (2021). Sustainability through online renting clothing: Circular fashion fueled by instagram micro-celebrities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278, 123772.
- Simeon Gill (2015) A review of research and innovation in garment sizing, prototyping and fitting, *Textile Progress*, 47:1, 1-85
- Scuotto, V., Arrigo, E., Candelo, E., & Nicotra, M. (2020). Ambidextrous innovation orientation effected by the digital transformation: A quantitative research on fashion SMEs. *Business Process Management Journal*, 26(5), 1121-1140.
- McCormick, Helen, Cartwright, Jo, Perry, Patsy, Barnes, Liz, Lynch, Samantha and Ball, Gemma (2014) Fashion retailing – past, present and future. *Textile Progress*, 46 (3). pp. 227-321.

Fig. 4 - The list of top 10 most cited papers.

3. Conclusion

Digitalisation is widely regarded as both a necessary and sufficient condition for fostering product and process innovation and transforming business models within the fashion industry. This digital transformation fosters a dynamic and collaborative ecosystem between consumers and fashion SMEs, playing a crucial role in developing sustainable strategies. Social media platforms have evolved from simple marketing tools into powerful instruments for promoting ambidextrous innovation, facilitating idea exchange and enabling businesses to swiftly adapt to changing market demands.

In the current era of digitalisation, achieving sustainability goals is increasingly associated with mass customisation and hyper-personalisation in product design. Digitalisation mediates between individual customer requests and the standardisation required for efficient production processes. This intersection of sustainability and digitalisation in the fashion industry has led to the development of a unique framework known as "digitainability," which drives innovation and business development.

Content analysis reveals that digitalisation equips businesses with versatile tools to create an environment conducive to sustainability-oriented innovation. These tools align with the principles of smart

business process interaction and are grounded in a circular approach. Product innovation, bridging the physical and virtual realms, results from this digital transformation, leading to transformative process innovations. Digitally-driven process innovation can significantly propel the transition towards Industry 5.0 by enabling various forms of collaboration between humans and bots within a smart workforce system.

Summarising the theoretical background derived from the critical analysis of the aforementioned papers, we introduce the digitainability conceptual framework (Figure 10). This framework illustrates how digitalisation, through specific principles and tools, enables sustainability-oriented innovations to address various sustainability challenges by incorporating a circular fashion approach. As companies in the fashion sector explore innovative business models, their success depends on several factors: the extent of circular economy principles adoption, the company's digital capabilities, the type of digital innovation (incremental or radical), and the level of consumer engagement. Effective communication channels between designers and consumers are crucial for advancing these innovative business models, reflected as two parallel and complementary development concepts: consumer-driven and digitally-driven. On the figure 5 there is suggested mapping of the digital innovation and its sustainability displays specifically within the fashion industry sector accordingly to three core pillars: product, process and business model innovations - disclosed on the base of digitainability principles framework.

In conclusion, digitalisation is not just a technological trend but a transformative force reshaping the fashion industry. It promotes collaboration, innovation, and sustainability, creating an ecosystem where businesses can thrive by embracing circular principles and leveraging digital tools. As fashion companies adapt to this new landscape, their success will hinge on their ability to harness digitalisation for innovation while also meeting the increasing demands for sustainable and personalized products.

Fig. 5 – The digital innovation and sustainability in fashion industry

Future research should focus on strategies for redefining circularity's significance for stakeholders, moving beyond philanthropic environmental attitudes to economically grounded conditions that ensure business sustainability. Key areas include identifying drivers and barriers to forming integrated digital infrastructures and enhancing consumer awareness of digital and circular fashion.

Human-computer interaction in the fashion industry warrants further exploration, particularly regarding decision-making processes and the complex matrix of technology acceptance factors. Future fashion design should be guided by conditional design principles, and the "luxury brand" strategy should address high-quality consumer expectations for eco-friendly circular clothing.

Several limitations must be acknowledged in the pursuit of digitalisation and circularity in the fashion industry. One significant constraint is the accessibility and affordability of advanced digital technologies. Smaller fashion businesses may lack the financial resources and expertise to fully embrace digitalisation, leading to industry disparities. Transitioning to circular practices is also challenged by entrenched linear business models and supply chains. Overcoming these established systems requires substantial time and investment, which may deter some businesses from making necessary changes.

Achieving complete circularity in fashion is complex, involving challenges such as recycling technologies, material sourcing, and consumer behavior. Additionally, the "luxury brand" strategy, while promising, may not be universally accessible or appealing. Effectively communicating sustainability and circularity concepts to stakeholders may face resistance, particularly if perceived trade-offs between sustainability and profitability persist. These limitations highlight the need for comprehensive strategies and collaborative efforts to address the challenges of digitalisation and circularity in the fashion industry.